

Gradient of Pressure Present in a Quantum Bound State Particle Even Without a Potential?

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In a previous note, it was suggested one can use definitions of temperature and heat flow from the Boltzmann transport equation and calculate similar quantities for a bound state quantum wavefunction. It was also suggested that one could not use the “transport equations” such as the Euler equation for the quantum bound state system. In another note, however, it was shown that the quantum bound state contained important terms of the Euler equation, namely $-d/dx \ln(d(x))$ and $F(x)d(x)$ where $d(x)$ is the density and $F(x)$ the force. In this note, we consider the definition of pressure from the Boltzmann transport equation and calculate its gradient. We find the usual $F(x)d(x)$ term in addition to an extra term. In setting $F(x)=0$, we find the extra term coincides with the gradient of pressure for a quantum particle in a box with no potential. Thus, it appears that a quantum particle, even without a potential, represents a pressure gradient which affects the form of the Schrodinger equation and causes quantum particles to differ from those of classical and classical statistical mechanics.

Calculation of $-d/dx V(x)$ from the Schrodinger Equation in Microscopic Terms

Before considering pressure, let us try to obtain a microscopic picture of pressure in a bound state quantum system in terms of “plane wave quasiparticles”. We first write the time independent Schrodinger equation:

$$(-1/2m) (1/W(x)) (d/dx)(d/dx) W(x) = E - V(x) \quad ((1))$$

where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction and $V(x)$ the potential. Taking the gradient of both sides of ((1)):

$$(-1/2m) (-d/dx d/dx W)/W - (d/dx W)/W + (-1/2m)(1/W) (d/dx)^3 W = -d/dx V \quad ((2))$$

with $W = \text{Sum over } p \ W_p$ i.e. decompose W in its Fourier series for example, $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ f_p \sin(px)$.

$$\text{Sum over } p \ (p^2/2m - p_{ave}^2/2m) W_p/W = -W^2 d/dx V \quad ((3))$$

Here p_{ave} is the classical momentum at point x which satisfies:

$$p_{ave}^2/2m + V = E.$$

Thus, one has:

$$\sum_p (p^2/2m + V - E) \frac{d}{dx} (W_p/W) = W^2 (-d/dx V) \quad ((4))$$

Thus, the force time density, which appears in the Euler equation, Brownian motion and other places appears to be related to quasiparticle (free particle) flux carrying an excess or deficiency of kinetic energy compared to the classical average i.e. $p^2/2m - \text{pave}^2/2m$.

An alternative way to obtain this result is to consider:

$$0 = W \sum_p (p^2/2m - \text{pave}^2/2m) W_p \quad ((5))$$

One can then take the gradient of ((5)):

$$0 = \frac{d}{dx} W \cdot 0 + W \sum_p (p^2/2m - \text{pave}^2/2m) \frac{d}{dx} W_p + W \sum_p \frac{d}{dx} V(x) W_p$$

Or

$$-d(x) \frac{d}{dx} V(x) = W^2 \sum_p (p^2/2m - \text{pave}^2/2m) \frac{d}{dx} W_p / W$$

Thus, one can see by the fact that one has $d/dx W_p$, that the single quasiparticle flux is important in describing the overall effects of the force on the quantum bound state. Actually, for a particle in a well without a potential the single particle velocity would be $(d/dx W_p)/W_p$ while here it is $(d/dx W_p)/W$.

Definition of Pressure

In (1), a pressure tensor is defined by:

$$P_{ij} = d(x) \langle (v_i - u)(v_j - u) \rangle \quad \text{where } d(x) \text{ is the density and } u = \langle v \rangle$$

For the one-dimensional quantum bound state $i=j$ and we use $u = (d/dx W)/W$. Then:

$$\text{Pressure} = P = -W^2 \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{d}{dx} W \right) - \left(\frac{d}{dx} W \right)^2 \quad ((6))$$

The gradient of pressure then becomes:

$$\frac{d}{dx} P = -3 \left[\frac{d}{dx} W \right] \left[\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W \right] - W \left(\frac{d}{dx} \right)^3 W \quad \text{or}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} P = -4 \left[\frac{d}{dx} W \right] \left[\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W \right] - \left[\frac{d}{dx} V(x) \right] W^2 / 2m \quad ((7))$$

The $\frac{d}{dx}P$ and $-\frac{d}{dx}V(x) \frac{W^*W}{2m}$ are expected and very similar to those found in Brownian motion and the Euler equation, but the first term on the right hand side of ((7)) is not. To try to understand its origin. Consider setting $\frac{d}{dx}V(x) = 0$. Then,

$$\frac{d}{dx}P = -4 \frac{d}{dx}W \left[\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W \right] \quad ((8))$$

This is equivalent to the result for the gradient of pressure for a particle in a box with no potential i.e.

$$\frac{d}{dx}P = -3 \frac{d}{dx}Wp \left[\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} Wp \right] - Wp \left[\left(\frac{d}{dx} \right)^3 Wp \right]$$

For $W=C\sin(kx)$ where C is a normalization constant, the last term above is equivalent to $-\frac{d}{dx}Wp \left[\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} Wp \right]$ or one recovers $4 \frac{d}{dx}W \left[\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W \right]$.

Thus, one can see that there is a gradient of pressure for a quantum particle in a box with no potential. This does not occur for a classical point particle or classical statistical mechanical particle. It is unique to the behaviour of the quantum mechanical particle which we argue undergoes zitterbewegung, i.e. moves backward and forwards while moving on average with v in one direction (2). (In principle, one should be able to have such an object in the classical realm provided that interference occurred i.e. interactions with the potential while the object is “moving” backwards come in with a negative sign, while those when it is moving forward come in with a positive sign.)

When one moves from a single particle in a box, to the case of a potential, it is interesting to note that the effects of the quantum single particle gradient of pressure supply ((8)), where one now has W and not Wp . ((8)) can, however, be thought of microscopically in terms of the quasiparticle plane waves as:

$$-4 \frac{d}{dx}W \left[\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W \right] = -4 \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{1}{2} m v(x)^2 \right) \left(\frac{1}{W} \sum_p f_p \cos(px) \right)$$

Here, $\frac{1}{2} m v(x)^2$ is the classical kinetic energy, and it is being carried by the flux of each quasiparticle. The fluxes of the quasiparticles can interfere (i.e. at x $\cos(p_1x)$ may be positive and $\cos(p_2x)$ negative. There seems, however, to perhaps be a resonance in the system, as each $\frac{d}{dx}Wp$ is carrying the same collective $\frac{1}{2} m v(x)^2$ in this extra term.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems a quantum particle in a box with no potential has a pressure gradient. This gradient then carries through to the case of a potential (the time-independent Schrodinger equation) so that when the Schrodinger equation is formulated in terms of the gradient of pressure and force time density an extra term of $-4 \frac{d}{dx}W \left[\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W \right]$ appears, related to each “quasiparticle” carrying the same collective classical kinetic energy.

References

1. Huang, Kerson. *Statistical Mechanics* (Wiley: NY, 1987) p 100.
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. *Is Quantum Mechanics Contained in Special Relativity?* (preprint, zenodo, 2018)